

Evaluation of Sublethal Dose-Dependent Maternal and Prenatal Developmental Tolfenpyrad Toxicity in Wistar Rats

Deepanjaly S¹, Ranjith D^{1*}, Bindu Shree R¹,
Ananthu Vijayakrishnan¹, Aruna B¹, Sujith S¹, Pradeep M²,
Surjith K P³, Suresh S Nair¹ and Sanis Juliet¹

ISSN: 1542-2666

NAAS Rating (2025): 5.00

<https://www.jarvm.co/index.html>

jarvm.submit@gmail.com

2025; 20-3(Part-A): 51-60

Received: 21-11-2025

Accepted: 09-12-2025

Published: 10-12-2025

Deepanjaly S, Ranjith D, Bindu Shree R, Ananthu Vijayakrishnan, Aruna B, Sujith S, Suresh S Nair and Sanis Juliet

¹Department of Veterinary Pharmacology & Toxicology, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Kerala Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Pookode, Lakkidi, P. O., Wayanad, Kerala, India

Pradeep M

²Department of Veterinary Pathology, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Pookode, Kerala. Kerala Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Wayanad, Kerala, India

Surjith K P

³Department of Veterinary Anatomy, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Kerala Veterinary and Animal Sciences University,

***Corresponding Author :**

Ranjith D,

Department of Veterinary Pharmacology & Toxicology, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Kerala Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Kerala, India

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17875534

Abstract

Tolfenpyrad (TFP), an agricultural pyrazole-based insecticide, was reported for its impact on maternal health and prenatal development in pregnant Wistar rats. Rats received daily oral doses of TFP at 15 mg/kg, 7.5 mg/kg, or 3.75 mg/kg from gestation days 5 to 20. Maternal body weight, as well as feed and water intake, was monitored throughout the exposure period to assess systemic toxicity and overall clinical signs. No maternal deaths or conspicuous drug related toxic effects were observed in any treatment groups. However, TFP administration resulted in a dose-dependent decreased body weight gain, food consumption, and water intake in dams, indicating physiological disturbances with potential implications for fetal development. These results emphasize the importance of further research to better understand the developmental risks associated with TFP exposure during pregnancy.

Keywords: Tolfenpyrad, Toxicity dose-dependent, weight gain, Wistar Rats, food consumption, and water intake in dams

Introduction

The modernization of agriculture has led to the extensive use of insecticides to safeguard crop yields and global food security. However, their widespread application has raised serious concerns regarding environmental contamination and unintended toxic effects on non-target organisms (Kariyanna *et al.*, 2024). Tolfenpyrad is a pyrazole-derived insecticide developed by Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation in Japan and is chemically identified as 4-chloro-3-ethyl-1-methyl-N-(4-(p-tolyloxy)benzyl)-1H-pyrazole-5-carboxamide (Wang *et al.*, 2023; Tong *et al.*, 2025). It exhibits potent activity against multiple pest groups, including Hemiptera, Lepidoptera, Coleoptera, and rust mites, and remains effective across all developmental stages, eggs, larvae, nymphs, and adults, making it a valuable tool against pesticide-resistant populations (Chi *et al.*, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2022; Hikiji *et al.*, 2013). Mechanistically, TFP acts as a mitochondrial Complex I inhibitor, disrupting electron transport and cellular energy metabolism in target pests such as *Anopheles gambiae* (Lees *et al.*, 2020; Yamaguchi *et al.*, 2012).

Despite its pivotal role in modern pest control, TFP raises growing concerns regarding its safety in non-target species, particularly mammals (Guo *et al.*, 2023). Acute toxicity studies have classified TFP as moderately toxic, with oral LD50 values of 86 mg/kg in male and 75 mg/kg in female rats (JMPR, 2013). Beyond acute effects, sub-chronic exposure has been linked to significant reductions in body weight, feed, and water intake in male rats, suggesting possible disturbances in metabolic regulation and systemic energy balance (Vaishnavi *et al.*, 2025). Critically, maternal nutritional status, encompassing body weight gain, feed, and water intake, is fundamental to ensuring proper fetal development. Indeed, developmental toxicity bioassays consistently identify reductions in maternal gestational weight gain and food consumption as sensitive indicators of maternal

distress that closely correlate with adverse fetal outcomes (Chernoff *et al.*, 2008).

However, the effects of TFP exposure on these maternal parameters during pregnancy remain unexplored, representing a significant gap in understanding its reproductive and developmental risk profile. The present study addresses this critical void by evaluating the maternal toxicity profile of TFP in pregnant Wistar rats, focusing on maternal weight dynamics and nutritional parameters as key determinants of fetal development and reproductive health.

Materials and Methods

This research was conducted in strict accordance with the OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, No. 414 (Prenatal Developmental Toxicity Study; adopted 25 June 2018) to ensure methodological reliability and reproducibility (OECD, 2018). Furthermore, all experimental procedures complied with the regulatory framework of the Committee for the Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), thereby upholding the highest ethical standards and aligning with the study's scientific objectives.

Chemicals

The test compound, TFP (analytical grade, 97% purity), was procured from Tokyo Chemical Industry (India) Pvt. Ltd., CAS RN: 129558-76-5. The dosing regimen was determined based on the reported oral LD50 value of 75 mg/kg in female rats, using olive oil as the vehicle, as described by Ishii (2000).

Animals: Apparently healthy adult male (15) and female Wistar rats (30), weighing 200-250 g, procured from the Committee for the Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA) approved Laboratory Animal Facility (LAF), College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Pookode (1271/GO/ReBiBt-S/ReRc-L/09/CCSEA), were used in the study. All animals were housed in standard management conditions at 23°C and 50-60% relative humidity, and they were fed with standard laboratory feed and water *ad*

libitum. The daily cycle alternated between twelve hours of light and twelve hours of darkness. Seven days before the start of the trial, the animals were acclimated to the laboratory environment. The study was conducted over a period of 21 days. The experimental protocol was approved by IAEC, College of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Pookode vide No. IAEC/COVAS/PKD/24/11/2025.

Study design, dosage, and parameters were evaluated.

Initially, the experimental cyclical female rats were cohabited with male rats (2:1) overnight. Day zero of the gestation was the day on which a vaginal plug and/or sperms was observed. Upon pregnancy confirmation, female rats will be divided into five groups, each containing six animals. Group I was considered as normal control and was administered distilled water; Group II was vehicle control, which was given olive oil only. Orally TFP is administered at the dose rate of 1/5th of the LD50 (15 mg/kg) to group III, 1/10th of the LD50 (7.5 mg/kg) to group IV, and 1/20th of the LD50 (3.75 mg/kg) to group V rats for consecutive days. Prior to dosing (12 hrs), the feed and water were withdrawn. Doses of TFP were given out every day at 10 a.m. The animals had free access to feed and water one hour after medication. All of the animals were observed for 30 minutes following the drug administration to check for any behavioural changes. Weekly, the body weight, feed, and water consumption of the rats in the control and treatment groups were noted. The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis by using repeated 2-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test for finding which of the groups are significantly different.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was done by GraphPad Prism version 8.0.2. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM), n=6. Statistical significance was assessed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's multiple comparison test to

identify significant intergroup differences. Different uppercase superscript letters (A, B, C, D) indicate significant differences across gestational days (GD) (time effect), while different lowercase superscript letters (a, b, c) within the same GD indicate significant differences among dose groups (dose effect). Values sharing the same and without superscript letter are not significantly different (adjusted p > 0.033); those with different letters differ significantly (adjusted p < 0.001).

Results:

Pregnant female Wistar rats administered TFP at three sublethal dose levels exhibited mild clinical signs of toxicity over the 21-day experimental period. Notable observations included lethargy, anorexia, change in body coats and erythema around the mouth region. These alterations became increasingly prominent from the fifth day of exposure, indicating the onset of toxic effects attributable to TFP treatment.

Weekly change in body weight of rats after repeated oral administration of TFP

The weekly mean maternal body-weight values recorded from GD0 to GD20. In control groups and treated groups, body weight increased throughout gestation, reflecting normal physiological gain associated with fetal growth. In contrast, TFP-treated rats exhibited a dose-dependent attenuation in weight gain. Animals exposed to 15mg/kg bwt and 7.5mg/kg bwt doses showed markedly lower body-weight increments from mid-gestation onwards (GD14–GD20) compared with controls, whereas the 3.75mg/kg bwt group displayed a pattern comparable to that of the vehicle control.

The statistical analysis showed that both GD and dose significantly influenced the body weight of rats. The interaction between GD and dose was also significant, indicating that the effect of dose varied across different time points. This suggests that TFP exposure led to dose-dependent alterations in body weight over the treatment period.

Post hoc Tukey's multiple comparison tests revealed significant reductions in gain of body weight at higher sublethal doses (15mg/kg, 7.5mg/kg) compared to 3.75mg/kg bwt, normal control and vehicle control groups, particularly during later stages of exposure. While

Table 1: Weekly body weight (g) of treatment groups

GD	Body weight (g)				
	Control	Vehicle control	15mg/kg bwt	7.5mg/kg bwt	3.75mg/kg bwt
GD0	231.5±4.64 ^A	231±2.59 ^A	228.48±5.36 ^A	229.5±0.4 ^A	231.72±4.4 ^A
GD7	243.17±4.56 ^B	241.8±2.83 ^B	232.98±5.36 ^A	238.2±1.55 ^A	242.63±4.1 ^B
GD14	266.5±3.73 ^{Cb}	266.72±3.25 ^{Cb}	236.27±5.37 ^{Aa}	250.42±1.88 ^{Bb}	266.42±3.49 ^{Cb}
GD20	310.83±3.52 ^{Dc}	309.02±3.77 ^{Dc}	243±4.41 ^{Ba}	278.82±0.30 ^{Cb}	310.18±3.64 ^{Dc}

Fig. 1: Body weight changes (Mean ± SEM) in different groups of pregnant rats across gestational days (GD0, GD7, GD14, GD20) are shown. Each bar represents data of Table.1

Weekly change in feed of rats after repeated oral administration of TFP

The two-way repeated measures ANOVA revealed that both feed intake and water intake were significantly influenced by the dose, gestation days, and their interaction, indicating a strong dose- and time-dependent effect of TFP exposure on the physiological parameters of pregnant rats.

Rats administered 15mg/kg and 7.5mg/kg bwt doses exhibited a significant reduction in feed consumption compared to the normal control and vehicle control groups, particularly during mid and late gestation whereas the 3.75mg/kg bwt group showed no significance difference with respect to normal and vehicle control group feed intake.

Table 2: Weekly feed intake (g) of treatment groups

GD	Feed Intake (g)				
	Control	Vehicle Control	15mg/kg bwt	7.5mg/kg bwt	3.75mg/kg bwt
GD0	18.18±0.09 ^A	18.2±0.08 ^A	18.15±0.09 ^A	18.17±0.02 ^A	18.17±0.08 ^A
GD7	18.55±0.09 ^{Ab}	18.56±0.1 ^{Ab}	18.09±0.08 ^{Aa}	18.37±0.04 ^{Ab}	18.53±0.09 ^{Ab}
GD14	21.72±0.28 ^{Bc}	21.6±0.26 ^{Bc}	18.71±0.08 ^{Aa}	19.69±0.05 ^{Ab}	21.53±0.27 ^{Bc}
GD20	25.3±0.11 ^{Cc}	25.16±0.18 ^{Cc}	15.25±0.13 ^{Ba}	22.08±0.29 ^{Bb}	25.31±0.10 ^{Cc}

Fig.2: Feed intake (Mean ± SEM) trends in different groups of pregnant rats across gestational days (GD0, GD7, GD14, GD20) are illustrated. Each bar represents the average feed consumption for each experimental group and time point, as detailed in Table 2.

Weekly change in water intake of rats after repeated oral administration of TFP

The two-way repeated measures ANOVA for water intake showed that there is a significant increase in water intake observed in the 15 mg/kg bwt and 7.5 mg/kg bwt treatment groups compared with the normal control and vehicle control rats; particularly during mid-gestational days and later in late gestation, water intake decreased. The 3.75 mg/kg bwt group showed values close to normal, indicating less physiological disturbance at lower exposure.

Table 2: Weekly feed intake (g) of treatment groups

GD	Water intake(mL)				
	Control	Vehicle Control	15mg/kg bwt	7.5mg/kg bwt	3.75mg/kg bwt
GD0	24.67±0.27 ^A	24.73±0.25 ^A	24.45±0.20 ^A	24.31±0.15 ^A	24.71±0.25 ^A
GD7	30.5±0.21 ^B	30.51±0.21 ^B	29.41±0.12 ^B	29.7±0.07 ^B	30.52±0.21 ^B
GD14	36.22±0.07 ^{Cc}	36.30±0.06 ^{Cc}	27.21±0.11 ^{Ba}	29.38±0.14 ^{Bb}	36.26±0.05 ^{Cc}
GD20	44.26±0.11 ^{Dc}	44.34±0.08 ^{Dc}	29.58±0.18 ^{Ba}	32.33±0.14 ^{Bb}	44.29±0.10 ^{Dc}

Fig.3: Water intake changes (Mean \pm SEM) in different groups of pregnant rats across gestational days (GD0, GD7, GD14, GD20) are shown. Each bar represents data of Table.3

Discussion

In the present study, gestational exposure to TFP at sublethal oral doses from GD 0 to GD 20 in Wistar albino rats produced notable physiological alterations, including lethargy, anorexia, roughened body coats, and erythema around the mouth. A significant, dose-dependent reduction in maternal body weight and feed intake was observed at 15 mg/kg bwt and 7.5 mg/kg bwt, accompanied by transient increase in water intake from mid-gestation to GD20. These alterations indicate systemic stress and disruption of metabolic equilibrium. The findings are consistent with earlier toxicological evaluations, where TFP was reported to cause mild irritation of the skin and eyes in New Zealand rabbits (JMPR, 2013) and to suppress body weight gain, feed, and water consumption in subchronic studies on male rats (Vaishnavi *et al.*, 2024). Similar metabolic disturbances have been documented with various

pesticides, suggesting a shared toxicodynamic mechanism underlying such effects. Studies on fipronil, deltamethrin, triazophos, heptachlor, abamectin, profenofos, fenpropathrin, carbosulfan, methomyl, imidacloprid, and cymoxanil have all reported dose-dependent decreases in feed consumption and body weight among pregnant rats (Oduma *et al.*, 1995; Tiwari *et al.*, 2008; Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2010; Udo *et al.*, 2014; Vohra *et al.*, 2014; Eisa, 2017). The consistency of these observations across diverse chemical classes points toward interference with central and peripheral pathways regulating energy balance. The observed reduction in maternal body weight gain in the present study may be attributed to enhanced catabolism of lipids and proteins or disruption of endocrine signals governing metabolic homeostasis (Goel *et al.*, 2005; Bhanot *et al.*, 2020). Pesticides are known to perturb energy balance by altering glucose and lipid metabolism, modifying fatty acid synthesis

and storage, and inducing mitochondrial dysfunction within the central nervous system. Such mitochondrial and neuroendocrine disturbances can impair hypothalamic control of appetite and feeding behavior, leading to decreased nutrient intake and consequent weight loss (Abdel-Razik and Hamed, 2015; Ghorzi *et al.*, 2017; Bonvallot *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the concurrent reductions in feed intake and maternal body weight observed in TFP-treated rats are likely the outcome of a coordinated cascade involving metabolic disruption, oxidative stress, and neuroendocrine dysregulation affecting central appetite-regulatory pathways. Physiologically, pregnant rats exhibit a progressive increase in voluntary water intake from mid-gestation onward, primarily driven by hormonal and osmoregulatory adaptations that support gestational fluid balance (Barron *et al.*, 1985; Joyner *et al.*, 2008). The decline in water intake toward mid gestation may indicate toxic interference with hypothalamic nuclei regulating thirst and fluid homeostasis, a mechanism supported by earlier neurotoxicological studies linking hypothalamic damage to altered drinking behavior (Ungerstedt, 1971; Zigmond and Stricker, 1973; Vaishnavi *et al.*, 2024). Notably, the rebound elevation in water intake during late gestation in TFP-treated rats mirrors patterns reported with endosulfan exposure, wherein comparable endocrine and metabolic dysregulation has been implicated (Singh *et al.*, 2007). Collectively, these findings suggest that gestational exposure to TFP provokes a multifaceted physiological stress response, encompassing metabolic, endocrine, and neuroregulatory components that culminate in disrupted feed and water intake patterns during pregnancy.

Conclusion

Sublethal gestational exposure to TFP in rats provoked dose-dependent disruptions in maternal energy regulation, marked by suppressed weight gain, reduced feed intake, and altered drinking

behavior. The pattern reflects metabolic and neuroendocrine dysregulation, emphasizing that even low-dose TFP exposure can disturb maternal homeostasis during pregnancy and potentially heighten developmental vulnerability in offspring.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Kerala Veterinary and Animal Sciences University (KVASU), Wayanad, Kerala, for extending financial assistance and providing the essential facilities that made this research possible.

Reference

1. Abdel-Razik, R. K., & Hamed, N. A. (2015). Deleterious effect of abamectin on rat brain mitochondria. *Alexandria Science Exchange Journal*, 36(OCTOBER-DECEMBER), 423-428.
<https://doi.org/10.21608/asejaiqjsae.2015.2964>
2. Barron, W. M., Durr, J. A. Q. U. E. S., Stamoutsos, B. A., & Lindheimer, M. D. (1985). Osmoregulation and vasopressin secretion during pregnancy in Brattleboro rats. *American Journal of Physiology-Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology*, 248(1), R29-R37.
<https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.1985.248.1.R29>
3. Bhanot, R., & Sangha, G. K. (2020). Impact of in utero Exposure of Triazophos on Reproductive System Functions in Female Albino Rats, *Rattus norvegicus*. *Toxicol Int*, 26, 37.
<https://doi.org/10.18311/ti/2019/v26i1&2/23901>
4. Bhardwaj, S., Srivastava, M. K., Kapoor, U., & Srivastava, L. P. (2010). A 90 days oral toxicity of imidacloprid in female rats: morphological, biochemical and histopathological evaluations. *Food and chemical toxicology*, 48(5), 1185-1190.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2010.02.009>
5. Bonvallot, N., Canlet, C., Blas-Y-Estrada, F., Gautier, R., Tremblay-Franco, M., Chevolleau,

- S., Cordier, S. & Cravedi, J. P. (2018). Metabolome disruption of pregnant rats and their offspring resulting from repeated exposure to a pesticide mixture representative of environmental contamination in Brittany. *PloS one*, *13*(6), e0198448. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0198448>
6. Chernoff, N., Rogers, E. H., Gage, M. I., & Francis, B. M. (2008). The relationship of maternal and fetal toxicity in developmental toxicology bioassays with notes on the biological significance of the “no observed adverse effect level”. *Reproductive Toxicology*, *25*(2), 192-202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2007.12.001>
 7. Chi, W., Mingyuan, H., Fengshou, D., Jun, X., Xiaohu, W., Bing, C., Changbin, W., Tian, S., Yongquan, Z. and Xingang, L.(2021). The influence of tolfeprad on fitness, development, and reproduction in parents and offspring of *Coccinella septempunctata*. *Ecotoxicology and environmental Safety*, *210*, 111875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.111875>
 8. Eisa, A. A., Abo-Elghar, G. E., Ammar, I. M., Metwally, H. G., & Arafa, S. S. (2017). Embryotoxicity and teratogenicity of fipronil in rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Zagazig Journal of Agricultural Research*, *44*(5), 1851-1861. <https://doi.org/10.21608/zjar.2017.52265>
 9. Ghorzi, H., Merzouk, H., Hocine, L., & Merzouk, S. A. (2017). Long term biochemical changes in offspring of rats fed diet containing alpha-cypermethrin. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, *142*, 133-140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2017.05.010>
 10. Goel, A., Dani, V., & Dhawan, D. K. (2005). Protective effects of zinc on lipid peroxidation, antioxidant enzymes and hepatic histoarchitecture in chlorpyrifos-induced toxicity. *Chemico-biological interactions*, *156*(2-3), 131-140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2005.08.004>
 11. Guo, Y., Zhang, T., Wang, X., Zhang, J., Miao, W., Li, Q. X., & Fan, Y. (2024). Toxic effects of the insecticide tolfeprad on zebrafish embryos: Cardiac toxicity and mitochondrial damage. *Environmental Toxicology*, *39*(5), 2583-2595. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tox.24133>
 12. Hikiji, W., Yamaguchi, K., Saka, K., Hayashida, M., Ohno, Y., & Fukunaga, T. (2013). Acute fatal poisoning with Tolfeprad. *Journal of forensic and legal medicine*, *20*(8), 962-964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jflm.2013.08.012>
 13. Ishii, T., Itoh, K., Takahashi, S., Sato, H., Yanagawa, T., Katoh, Y., Bannai, S. & Yamamoto, M. (2000). Transcription factor Nrf2 coordinately regulates a group of oxidative stress-inducible genes in macrophages. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, *275*(21), 16023-16029. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.275.21.16023>
 14. JMPR [Joint FAO/WHO meeting on Pesticide Residues]. 2013. Tolfeprad. p. 459-498. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/pesticide-residues-jmpr?database/Document/208>.
 15. Joyner, J., Neves, L. A., Stovall, K., Ferrario, C. M., & Brosnihan, K. B. (2008). Angiotensin-(1-7) serves as an aquaretic by increasing water intake and diuresis in association with downregulation of aquaporin-1 during pregnancy in rats. *American Journal of Physiology-Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology*, *294*(3), R1073-R1080. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.00572.2007>
 16. Kariyanna, B., Senthil-Nathan, S., Vasantha-Srinivasan, P., Subba Reddy, B. V., Krishnaiah, A., Meenakshi, N. H., ... & Park, K. B. (2024). Comprehensive insights into pesticide residue dynamics: unraveling impact and management. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture*, *11*(1), 182. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40538-024-00708-4>
 17. Lees, R. S., Ismail, H. M., Logan, R. A., Malone, D., Davies, R., Anthousi, A., Adolphi, A., Lycett, G.J. & Paine, M. J. (2020). New

- insecticide screening platforms indicate that Mitochondrial Complex I inhibitors are susceptible to cross-resistance by mosquito P450s that metabolise pyrethroids. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), 16232. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-73267-x>
18. Oduma, J. A., Wango, E. O., Makawiti, D. W., Einer-Jensen, N., & Oduor-Okelo, D. (1995). Effects of graded doses of the pesticide heptachlor on body weight, mating success, oestrous cycle, gestation length and litter size in laboratory rats. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C: Pharmacology, Toxicology and Endocrinology*, 110(2), 221-227. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0742-8413\(94\)00028-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0742-8413(94)00028-9)
 19. OECD [Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development]. 2018. *Test No 414: Prenatal Developmental Toxicity Study*. OECD Publishing, Paris. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264070820-en>. [01 Jun. 2024].
 20. Vohra, P., Khera, K. S., & Sangha, G. K. (2014). Physiological, biochemical and histological alterations induced by administration of imidacloprid in female albino rats. *Pesticide biochemistry and physiology*, 110, 50-56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2014.02.007>
 21. Singh, N. D., Sharma, A. K., Dwivedi, P., Patil, R. D., & Kumar, M. (2007). Citrinin and endosulfan induced maternal toxicity in pregnant Wistar rats: pathomorphological study. *Journal of Applied Toxicology: An International Journal*, 27(6), 589-601. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jat.1242>
 22. Tiwari, V., Suresh, B., & Pilo, B. (2008). Evaluation of maternal toxicity in rats treated with deltamethrin 1%+ triazophos 35% EC. *Toxicology International*, 15(2), 127. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/97e398a5ae8437d1f0f4c7fde3c4904e/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=226455>
 23. Tong, L., Li, L., Suzhen, L., Xin, R., Manni, W., Fengjiao, L., Youpu, C. & Zenglong, C. (2025). Integrating processing factors and large-scale cabbage cultivation to understand the fate tendency and health risks of tolfenpyrad using deterministic and probabilistic models. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 486, 137131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137131>
 24. Udo, M. S., Sandini, T. M., Reis, T. M., Bernardi, M. M., & Spinosa, H. S. (2014). Prenatal exposure to a low fipronil dose disturbs maternal behavior and reflex development in rats. *Neurotoxicology and teratology*, 45, 27-33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ntt.2014.05.010>
 25. Ungerstedt, U. (1971). Adipsia and aphagia after 6-hydroxydopamine induced degeneration of the nigro-striatal dopamine system. *Acta Physiologica Scandinavica*, 82(S367), 95-122. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-201X.1971.tb11001.x>
 26. Vaishnavi, J. M., Ranjith, D., Gnanesh, M. K., Nisha, A. R., Preethy, J., Pradeep, M. N., Lekshmi Bhai, K., & Sanis, J. (2025). Subchronic toxicity of sublethal oral doses of tolfenpyrad in rats. *International Journal of Advanced Biochemistry Research*, SP-9(2), 574-577. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26174693.2025.v9.i2S.h.3840>
 27. Wang, Q., Sun, Z., Huang, Z., Ma, S., Chen, K., & Ju, X. (2023). Effects of tolfenpyrad exposure on development and response mechanism in the silkworm, *Bombyx mori*. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 189, 105280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2022.105280>
 28. Yamaguchi, K., Hikiji, W., Takino, M., Saka, K., Hayashida, M., Fukunaga, T., & Ohno, Y. (2012). Analysis of tolfenpyrad and its metabolites in plasma in a tolfenpyrad poisoning case. *Journal of analytical toxicology*, 36(7), 529-537. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jat/bks060>
 29. Zhang, C. X., Wang, Z. J., Li, J. J., Wang, N. M., & Xue, C. B. (2022). Sublethal effects of

tolfenpyrad on the development, reproduction, and predatory ability of *Chrysoperla sinica*. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 236, 113482.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2022.113482>

30. Zigmond, M. J., & Stricker, E. M. (1973).

Recovery of feeding and drinking by rats after intraventricular 6-hydroxydopamine or lateral hypothalamic lesions. *Science*, 182(4113), 717-720.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.182.4113.717>